

Genetic mapping of agronomically important traits in einkorn wheat

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Supplementary Data 3: Graphs for QTLs detected in the DV92×G3116 RIL population of einkorn wheat

The 167 QTL graphs included in this supplementary data correspond to the QTLs listed in Supplementary Table S6 in the same order.

Blue arrows indicate the position of QTL peaks.

Note that the graphs show the QTLs before bootstrap analyses, i.e. LOD scores and positions may differ slightly from those in Supplementary Table S6.

Maximum LOD value

Maximum LOD value

I n t e r v a l s

2	14.14																						
3	14.14	14.14																					
4	13.64	13.65	-13.19																				
5	13.50	13.51	13.24	12.38																			
6	13.17	13.49	13.25	12.38	9.91																		
7	13.63	13.62	12.42	11.50	11.06	11.06																	
8	13.92	13.92	12.66	11.90	11.97	11.97	9.72																
9	15.23	15.23	13.88	13.39	13.42	13.42	11.86	11.87															
10	16.68	16.68	15.29	14.87	14.98	14.98	13.42	13.44	12.93														
11	17.52	17.52	16.09	15.70	15.79	15.79	14.08	14.12	13.56	13.61													
12	20.57	20.57	18.99	18.63	18.77	18.77	17.08	17.11	16.45	16.13	16.34												
13	20.57	20.60	19.01	18.65	18.88	18.88	17.48	17.48	16.81	16.61	16.64	-8.20											
14	20.54	20.53	18.99	18.65	19.02	19.02	17.75	17.75	17.12	17.02	17.18	18.13	18.04										
15	21.48	21.47	20.70	20.22	20.41	20.40	19.14	19.14	18.75	18.70	19.43	20.21	20.21	19.69									
16	21.62	21.59	20.79	20.30	20.52	20.52	19.14	19.14	18.75	18.68	19.43	20.22	20.21	19.69	18.39								
17	22.44	22.44	21.50	21.05	21.36	21.36	19.94	19.94	19.31	19.13	19.83	20.36	20.36	19.95	19.17	19.50							
18	20.91	20.64	19.57	19.07	19.18	19.18	17.62	17.64	17.72	17.84	18.32	19.41	19.40	19.21	19.35	19.49	20.63						
19	13.55	13.73	13.03	12.04	10.64	10.62	9.17	9.62	11.91	13.24	13.89	17.04	17.39	17.64	19.17	19.06	20.67	18.19					
20	13.53	13.71	13.01	12.03	10.63	10.63	9.17	9.62	11.90	13.29	13.95	17.13	17.39	17.64	19.06	18.99	20.21	16.51	1.74				
21	13.12	13.26	12.57	11.58	10.27	10.27	8.81	9.28	11.78	13.26	13.78	16.49	16.74	17.02	17.83	18.01	18.89	15.11	2.26	2.27			
22	13.78	13.94	13.29	12.41	10.76	10.76	9.69	10.20	12.61	14.06	14.75	17.04	17.18	17.47	17.78	17.60	18.42	14.99	3.01	3.31	3.30		
23	13.79	13.94	13.29	12.41	10.76	10.76	9.69	10.19	12.61	14.06	14.75	17.04	17.18	17.47	17.65	17.40	18.07	15.25	2.53	3.31	3.31	3.37	

I n t e r v a l s

Maximum LOD value

Maximum LOD value

Maximum LOD value

I n t e r v a l s

Table with 62 rows (intervals 2-63) and 62 columns (intervals 1-63). Each cell contains a numerical value representing the Maximum LOD value for a specific interval pair. The diagonal elements are highlighted in a lighter shade, and certain cells contain values in bold or blue.

I n t e r v a l s

Maximum LOD value

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10 11 12 13 14 15 16 17 18 19 20 21 22 23 24 25 26 27 28 29 30 31 32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40 41 42 43 44 45 46 47 48 49 50 51 52 53 54 55 56 57 58 59 60 61 62 63 64 65

wPt-6757 wPt-0601 wPt-861413 tPt-9948 Psr119_1000bp ksud9_100bp wPt-861194 wPt-8868 wPt-470475 wPt-861587 cgg271_barcode_22A+J wPt-376185 tPt-7193 wPt-861594 wPt-469953 wPt-860749 wPt-8986 wPt-470453 wPt-861626 wPt-470566 wPt-861377 wPt-470626 wmc405 cfa2174 wPt-469159 gwm573 wPt-470397 wPt-470538 wPt-860800 wPt-469732 wPt-9172 wPt-861765 wPt-861971 abg55_205bp wPt-376885 ldk16e ldk16c lrap1032_650bp wPt-3393 ksug14_450bp wPt-861656 wPt-862179 wPt-470283 wPt-469827 wPt-470248 wPt-861533 owm31_230bp wPt-861198 wPt-469968 wPt-7281 wPt-861027 wPt-861122 tPt-3608 wPt-6029 wPt-6369 wPt-470056 wPt-469569 wPt-862230 wPt-2018 wPt-861522 wPt-861928 gwm344 wPt-6797 wPt-6276 mwg584_140bp

L(cM)

Maximum LOD value

I n t e r v a l s

I n t e r v a l s

